

XORIYIY TILLARNI O'QITISHDA INNOVATSION YONDASHUVLAR NAZARIYANING AMALIYOTGA TATBIQI

mavzusidagi respublika ilmiy-amaliy anjumani

ESP VOCABULARY ACQUISITION

Khazratova Zukhra Mamaraimovna

Uzbekistan State World Languages University, Uzbekistan

Phone: +998903156384

zukhrakhazratova80@gmail.com

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15177228>

Abstract: *English for Specific Purposes (ESP) course design and basic overview are covered in this article within the framework of ELT (English Language Teaching). Moreover, this article offers a theoretical examination of the core concepts of ESP, such as its definition and role as a learning approach, along with related subjects like learning objectives, materials, methodology—a key element of ESP—and assessment of ESP-based English language training.*

Keywords: *ESP, Vocabulary, terminology, methodology.*

In recent decades, English has become the primary language in many fields and has permeated practically every aspect of society. Since many of the major scientific publications publish their papers in English, which is a standardized language that everyone can access, technological and scientific advances are nearly entirely disseminated in this language to avoid misunderstandings and potential mistakes that could have dire repercussions. This standard medium allows entrepreneurs from different countries to find common ground. It does this by expressing concepts that may differ in different cultures using a specific set of English phrases that everyone understands to have the same meaning. English for Specific Purposes (ESP), which addresses these concerns particularly, has grown significantly in significance over the last few decades.

At the worldwide level, communication takes place in English in an increasing number of fields, and business, trade, science, technology, medical, aviation, hospitality, and other fields have long transcended national boundaries to operate on a global scale. In this circumstance, grammar is crucial for accuracy, but vocabulary is even more useful since, in many cases, even if someone uses the wrong past tense instead of the present perfect, the message will still be comprehended if the right words are utilized properly. However, some ESP theorists and practitioners view vocabulary acquisition as a supporting element in the language education process, while others view it as the main focus. Why is vocabulary important? In order to succeed in ESP, students must develop a steady vocabulary of terminology that are

XORIJIY TILLARNI O'QITISHDA INNOVATSION YONDASHUVLAR NAZARIYANING AMALIYOTGA TATBIQI

mavzusidagi respublika ilmiy-amaliy anjumani

unique to and commonly used in their field of study. It is the foundation they will need for their future employment and the one they may build upon.

Teachers and students must first understand the direct connection between their language demands and valuable classroom time. They are supposed to be reading books that contain important concepts and the terminology used in their area, then writing in those terms and thoughts. Second, these students' comprehension and application of this specialized terminology demonstrate their membership in a specific group. His argument is consistent with that of other theorists (Mohan and van Naerssen, 1997), who contend that familiarity with a subject's vocabulary broadens students' understanding of their field of study. The specialist language of a discipline is essential to students' acquisition of disciplinary knowledge; students must demonstrate their comprehension of concepts, phenomena, and the relationships between phenomena, among other things, by accurately utilizing the terminology and specialist language of their discipline in their writing. To understand and interact with academic information, they must also embrace the specialized language. (Kron & Woodward, 2008: 246) Additionally, it facilitates access to resources that would otherwise be unavailable to students because of the language barrier, such as reading English-language journals, visiting websites or applications written in English, interacting with peers from other nations, and exchanging ideas in their field of study using English.

Tudor (1997) and other ESP specialists have questioned the traditional approach of relying solely on course design experts to gather objective information on learners. They argue that learners' subjective perspectives should be considered in curriculum and material design. Hutchinson and Waters (1987) advocate for a more "learning-centred" approach to ESP, emphasizing the importance of learner participation in second language acquisition.

It can be difficult to encourage pupils to learn language in this day and age, though. The lengthy process of learning vocabulary has historically been seen as tedious since it calls for patience and time, two qualities that are no longer valued in the fast-paced world of today. Students these days frequently question why they should learn terms when they can simply search for them on their phones anytime they need them. Convenience is among the obvious and uncomplicated justifications for the necessity of vocabulary development. You cannot be expected to constantly check your phone every five seconds when conversing with an English-speaking

XORIJIY TILLARNI O'QITISHDA INNOVATSION YONDASHUVLAR NAZARIYANING AMALIYOTGA TATBIQI

mavzusidagi respublika ilmiy-amaliy anjumani

person in order to seek up vocabulary or use translation apps to convey a point to your discussion partner.

Systematically exploring strategies and procedures, it is necessary to determine what vocabulary—specifically, ESP vocabulary—is comprehended, what should be stressed, and how much is needed. Among these are technical, sub-technical, semi-technical, specialized, and special purpose terminology. To put it simply, these terms typically refer to the lexicon of a specific field of study or profession. In ESP, a word's range is significant. That is, within a specific field of study, a specialized word would have a limited range of applications. Accordingly, specialist terms are supposed to be associated with a specific field of study at a university or a career.

Individuals who are not in the academic or professional domains may possess some vocabulary, but those who are expected to be proficient in these areas should be able to comprehend and apply the language with ease. Certain daily words that are entirely normal can have extremely precise meanings depending on the situation. This could not be feasible in the Romanian system since the majority of students have some knowledge of general English from secondary school, and the majority of these institutions are either math-and-science or humanities-focused high schools, where the English course focuses on grammar.

Which approach is applied? Despite not being specifically designed for vocabulary development, the majority of approaches are effective in this regard. The Communicative Approach, the Task-based Approach, and even the now-outdated Audio-lingual and its replacement PPP (Presentation, Practice, and Production) aid in vocabulary acquisition; however, in their case, this is not a targeted activity; rather, it is “incidental” or a byproduct of other activities that concentrate on skill development, task solving, and other areas.

Additionally, Tim Johns's highly effective corpus-based methodology, Data Driven Learning (DDL), which was introduced in the late 1980s and early 1990s, is based on corpus linguistics. In ESP, where the use of real materials is essential, corpus utilization is especially encouraged. It is also commonly used in ELT. Grammar and vocabulary are the two previously mentioned dichotomies that teachers frequently teach to their students. Both grammar and vocabulary are difficult for students to acquire on their own, thus other approaches (Communicative Approach, Lexico-grammatical Approach) can be used to teach both subjects easily and without making them feel burdensome.

XORIJY TILLARNI O'QITISHDA INNOVATSION YONDASHUVLAR NAZARIYANING AMALIYOTGA TATBIQI

mavzusidagi respublika ilmiy-amaliy anjumani

In addition, this is a huge advantage because effective resources and a compelling approach can significantly boost motivation: In order to address current learning challenges, "appropriate teaching materials, learning strategies, and the interactions between students and teachers are the essential components." Strategies, tactics, and materials strategies can be used to help with vocabulary growth if it is decided that this is the main goal of the ESP lesson. Instructors might choose to combine different approaches or just the ones they believe will benefit their students the best. Vocabulary should be taught in a way that promotes lifelong learning and helps students understand future challenges.

Despite the fact that students find vocabulary acquisition to be a dull task, ESP vocabulary can be taught without making it a drudgery or even requiring the ideal level of student motivation. By making improvements to their approach, educators can make learning ESP vocabulary enjoyable: Learning vocabulary is a laborious and prolonged process. Despite spending a lot of time trying to expand their vocabulary, some students still struggle to understand the words while reading and listening, as well as to memorize terms and collocations for oral and written communication. One of the causes is the use of inefficient vocabulary-learning techniques.

To sum up, fluency and a good command of English are achieved through vocabulary building, which is achieved by exposing students to a carefully chosen corpus of authentic materials and real-world scenarios where lexis and language chunks, rather than words, are preferred and context-appropriate language is used. The method of exposure and the methods employed are crucial since they will determine the outcome. Translation as a consolidation and revision tool, the use of the mother tongue, and accurate terminology equivalency between L1 and L2 should not be disregarded. These are good methods that will work if used correctly.

Used Literature:

1. Basturkmen, H., 2006, Ideas and Options in English for Specific Purposes. Mahwah, New Jersey, London, Lawrence Erlbaum Associates.
2. Hutchinson, T. & Waters, A. (1987) English for Specific Purposes: A Learning-Centred Approach. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
3. Coxhead, A., 2013, "Vocabulary and ESP" in Paltridge B. and Starfield S. (eds.) The Handbook of English for Specific Purposes, Wiley-Blackwell, pp. 115 132.
4. Kennedy, C. and R. Bolitho, 1991, English for Specific Purposes, London, MacMillan Press Ltd.

XORIJIY TILLARNI O'QITISHDA INNOVATSION YONDASHUVLAR NAZARIYANING AMALIYOTGA TATBIQI

mavzusidagi respublika ilmiy-amaliy anjumani

5. Lewis, M., 1997, Implementing the Lexical Approach. Language Teaching Publications. 7.
- Lewis, M., 2005, "Towards a Lexical View of Language – A Challenge for Teachers", *Babylonia*, 3/2005, pp. 7-10. 326